

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

ROLE OF MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING IN EVALUATION OF SEIZURES

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Abstract:

Objective: To explore the role of magnetic resonance imaging in evaluation of seizures.

Patients and Methods: The cross sectional study comprises fifty patients with clinical impression of seizures presented at tertiary care hospital. The seizure patients were selected irrespective of age and gender while the exclusion criteria were the contraindications to MRI studies, such as patients with pacemakers and metallic implants, aneurysmal clips and anxiety disorders exacerbated by MRI. The patient selected for the study clinically diagnosed cases of seizures as per criteria. Various details of MRI findings were studied as existence of lesion, site, and signal intensity, surrounding edema, any hemorrhage, atrophy, infarction, mass effect, contrast enhancement / enhancing lesions, calcification, developmental malformations and hydrocephalus. The frequency / percentages (%) and means $\pm$ SD computed for study variables.

Results: During six months study period total fifty patients with seizures were explored on MRI scan. The frequency for male and female population was 30 (60%) and 20 (40%) with mean $\pm$ SD for age of male and female individuals was 43.82 ± 7.65 and 47.55 ± 8.84 respectively. The male population (60%) was predominant while regarding the MRI findings the infarct with gliosis was identified in 14%, atrophy 16%, tuberculoma 24%, venous thrombosis 10%, glioma 10%, meningioma 10%, cerebral abscess 16%.

Conclusion: MRI plays a major role in the evaluation of patients with seizures.

Keywords: Seizures, Magnetic resonance imaging and Epilepsy.

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Please cite this article in press Mukhtiar Hussain Jaffery et al., *Role of Magnetic Resonance Imaging in Evaluation of Seizures.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Seizure is a paroxysmal alteration in neurologic characteristic resulting from odd excessive neuronal electrical activity [1]. The epilepsy is a persistent situation characterized with the aid of recurrent seizures unprovoked via an acute systemic or neurologic disorder [2]. An epileptic seizure is a clinical manifestation of abnormal, excessive neuronal pastime arising in the grey be counted of the cerebral cortex. It is age dependant and greater in youth and aged persons than in young adults and most of the patients struggling from this disorder infact majority of them have appropriate manage of this disorder with the use of antiepileptic drugs [3]. The suitable information is that most of these patients with intractable epilepsy have seizures that are focal and which can be probably treated. In clinical practice the assessment of patients supplying with seizures is a problem that the physician faces quite regularly. In order to diagnose and discover out the etiology of the lesion, there are many neuro radiological investigations that can be utilized these includes x-ray of skull, CSF examination, carotid angiography, EEG, CT and MRI. Although the treatment of a seizure is directed toward the immediately underlying metabolic or neurologic derangement, epilepsy commonly requires long term pharmacotherapy or in chosen instances neurosurgical intervention to put off or decrease recurrent seizures [4]. Neurosurgery is most often viewed in medically refractory epilepsy when removal or isolation of epileptogenic location is possible except unacceptable neurologic deficit. In this context, the progressive introduction of MRI for comparison of seizures has been a excellent boon, both for the prognosis of cerebral lesions as nicely as medical administration of patients with neurologic disorders [5]. MR imaging has emerged as the more diagnostically treasured and most treasured device for preoperative localization of epileptogenic center of attention because of its extremely good smooth tissue contrast, permitting for targeted depiction of anatomy, freedom from beam – hardening artifact in basal intelligence that happen with CT and capability for multiplanar imaging. The diagnosis of epilepsy with the help of MRI has made this diagnostic device beyond examine to other investigations [6]. MR is tons extra diagnostically precious and there is the splendid neuroimaging study of choice. It has been tested beyond doubt that MRI is the most meaningful process in the diagnosis, treatment and follow-up of sufferers with inflammatory and parasitic lesions of the intelligence such as cysticercosis tuberculoma, brain abscess, and encephalitis [7]. MR offers greater unique localization and histological nature of lesions

and subsequently, this is of monstrous help to both clinicians as nicely as neurosurgeons in their attempt to attain a quicker and more correct technique of discovering the nature of the pathologies [8]. The position of MR in epilepsy surgical operation in figuring out the epileptogenic focus also lies in its potential to depict topographic relationships between epileptogenic lesion and the eloquent areas of brain. Postoperative MR may also discover motives for failure such as insufficient resection and can monitor tumour recurrence on follow up imaging. MR is in particular useful for prognosticating postoperative seizure control. Thus this study has undertaken to explore the etiology and spectrum of MRI findings in sufferers with seizures.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

The cross sectional study comprises fifty patients with clinical impression of seizures presented at tertiary care hospital. The seizure patients were selected irrespective of age and gender while the exclusion criteria were the contraindications to MRI studies, such as patients with pacemakers and metallic implants, aneurysmal clips and anxiety disorders exacerbated by MRI. The patient selected for the study clinically diagnosed cases of seizures as per criteria. The detail history was taken and clinical examination was done. The points noted were duration of illness, type of seizures, and any associated illness. Detailed clinical and neurological examination was done to find any neurological deficit. Based on the history and examination, a clinicoetiological diagnosis was made. The biochemical investigations were done accordingly while all the patients underwent MRI scanning and the procedure was briefly explained to the patient including the risks of contrast examination. Various details of MRI findings were studied as existence of lesion, site, and signal intensity, surrounding edema, any hemorrhage, atrophy, infarction, mass effect, contrast enhancement / enhancing lesions, calcification, developmental malformations and hydrocephalus. The data was collected on pre-designed proforma and analyzed in SPSS to manipulate the frequency, percentages and mean $\pm$ SD.

RESULTS:

During six months study period total fifty patients with seizures were explored on MRI scan. The frequency for male and female population was 30 (60%) and 20 (40%) with mean $\pm$ SD for age of male and female individuals was 43.82 $\pm$ 7.65 and 47.55 $\pm$ 8.84 respectively. The demographical and clinical profile of study population is presented in

Table 1.

TABLE 1: THE DEMOGRAPHICAL AND CLINICAL PROFILE OF STUDY POPULATION

Parameter	Frequency (N=50)	Percentage (%)
AGE (yrs)		
13-19	11	22
20-29	15	30
30-39	08	16
40-49	06	12
50-59	07	14
60+	03	6.0
GENDER		
Male	30	60
Female	20	40
CLINICAL DIAGNOSIS		
Simple partial seizures	10	20
Complex partial seizures	12	24
Myoclonic seizures	08	16
GTCS	15	30
Myoclonic seizures	05	10
MRI FINDINGS		
Infarct with gliosis	07	14
Atrophy	08	16
Tuberculoma	12	24
Venous thrombosis	05	10
Glioma	05	10
Meningioma	05	10
Cerebral abscess	08	16

DISCUSSION:

Patients presenting with seizures can have wide range of MR imaging abnormalities depending upon the etiology. MRI can reliably identify and localize the intracranial abnormality so that further management can be planned accordingly [9]. Lancman ME, et al [10] explored onset of seizures in stroke patients and concluded that infarcts involving cerebral cortex, there was a high risk of early stroke in watershed infarcts than territorial strokes.

Theodore WH, et al [11] revealed that significant atrophy of hippocampus, neocortex and concluded that the brain volume reduction in epilepsy is the cumulative effect of an initial precipitating injury and age related cerebral atrophy. Significant atrophy developed in individual patients particularly those with temporal lobe epilepsy. Garg RK, et al [12] studied intracranial space occupying lesions with seizures and found intracranial tuberculoma and

followed after treatment responded well to medical treatment. Remarkable improvement of intracranial lesions within 6 weeks and complete resolution of the lesions within 12 weeks was reported. Beaumont A et al [13] studied a patient with medically intractable complex partial seizures and MRI study revealed a tumour with low signal intensity on T1 and increase signal intensity on T2 with no contrast enhancement in left anterior temporal lesion. Thron A, et al [14] reported a case of superior sagittal sinus (SSS) thrombosis with long history of continuous headache and MRV confirmed the presence of SSS thrombosis with small venous infarct where CT was normal.

CONCLUSION:

Assessment of the patient presenting with seizure disorder is a common problem in clinical practice and MRI plays a major role in the evaluation of patients with seizures.

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